

**THE USE OF MTB-TASK CARDS TO REMEDIATE LEARNING GAPS IN
GRADE 7 MATHEMATICS: INPUT FOR A PROPOSED HANDBOOK
ON THE RULES AND GUIDELINES IN THE DEVELOPMENT
PRODUCTION AND UTILIZATION OF MTB-TASK CARDS**

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The Use of MTB-Task Cards to Remediate Learning Gaps in Grade 7 Mathematics: Input for a Proposed Handbook on the Rules and Guidelines in the Development Production and Utilization of MTB-Task Cards

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Abstract

This study aimed to use MTB-Task Cards to remediate the learning gaps in Grade 7 mathematics, ultimately leading to the creation of a handbook for developing, producing, and utilizing these cards. It investigated the least mastered learning competencies based on MELCs for the first and second quarters of the 2023-2024 school year, assessed students' performance before and after the implementation of MTB-Task Cards, and determined the mean gain performance. The study also examined whether there was a significant difference between actual accomplishment and the target level of mastery after implementing the MTB-Task Cards. Employing a quasi-experimental design, the research utilized pre-test and post-test evaluations to measure the intervention's impact on a non-random group of 135 Grade 7 students at Emilio V. Quizon National High School. Data were gathered through a researcher-made test and validated MTB-Task Cards, focusing on competencies students struggled with the most. Findings revealed substantial improvements in mathematical competencies such as fundamental operations on integers, estimating square roots, and evaluating algebraic expressions. Students' performance levels increased significantly post-intervention, with mastery levels exceeding 80% in the second quarter, indicating the effectiveness of MTB-Task Cards. The analysis showed a significant difference between actual accomplishment and the target mastery level, with a p-value of 0.000. The study proposed a handbook outlining rules and guidelines for the development, production, and utilization of MTB-Task Cards, emphasizing the importance of standardization, curriculum alignment, quality production, and effective classroom use. Recommendations included continuous monitoring of student progress, professional development for educators, innovative engagement strategies, and ongoing research to enhance the instructional efficacy of MTB-Task Cards.

Keywords: *MTB-Task Cards, grade 7 learners, learning gaps, mathematical competencies, and mastery levels*

Introduction

The Department of Education has introduced limited face-to-face classes as part of its recovery learning continuity plan following two years of modular learning. This plan aims to address the learning gaps that have arisen due to the disruptions caused by the pandemic. It focuses on various aspects, such as remediation and intervention in learning, professional development, health, safety, and wellness. To achieve its goals, DepEd plans to increase reading interventions, regularly visit homes and provide follow-ups, establish physical and virtual study groups, and involve parent or guardian teacher volunteers.

The students and the teacher physically attend the classroom for in-person instruction. As stated in DepEd Order No. 034, series of 2022, the academic year will start on August 22 and conclude on July 7, 2023. A total of 203 school days are scheduled, with the possibility of adjustments in case of unforeseen circumstances. Rather than just imparting knowledge, teachers encourage and empower students to explore and harness their talents and energies (De Rosales, 2020).

Moreover, in transitioning from modular to in-person classes, students must adjust, particularly those who are struggling. Bulaon (2018) states that one challenge in teaching mathematics is the language barrier, as mathematics has a complex vocabulary. Words like addend, divisor, quotient, factor, and denominator can intimidate some students. The lack of understanding of these terms and concepts can hinder their math achievement. However, it is more than math terms that can trip up students. According to Alharbi and Maroof (2020), some students in their studies needed help articulating their thoughts clearly. This could have led to inaccurate responses to language-related questions. Edward, Asirvatham, and Johar (2018) emphasize the importance of teachers being aware of and addressing the challenges of teaching mathematics to English language learners. Teachers of secondary mathematics can better support students with low levels of English proficiency if they receive training in language instructional methods.

Dep Ed Order No. 74, s.2009 emphasizes the importance of using a student's mother tongue or Language 1 (L1) as a tool for teaching. This approach, known as Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE), utilizes multiple languages to enhance literacy and instructional methods. Students can improve their academic performance and successfully engage in Education for All (EFA) initiatives using their mother tongue. The benefits of this multilingual approach include faster reading skills development in the student's L1, facilitating easier acquisition of speaking, reading, and writing skills in second or third languages (L2 or L3), and the ability to acquire academic competencies more efficiently.

Furthermore, Uayan (2020) states that incorporating the mother tongue into education is a creative and effective method for students to develop their academic skills. This can be achieved by implementing a well-designed curriculum, providing necessary language training for teachers, creating suitable instructional materials, and engaging the community. Additionally, Tindowen (2020) discovered

that utilizing the Mother Tongue as a teaching method for math problem-solving enhances students' understanding of concepts and problem-solving techniques.

Moreover, the transmission of instructional delivery becomes a separate task within the teaching and learning process. Students face various challenges when attempting to solve exercises in face-to-face classes, especially concerning topics involving the four basic operations in mathematics. One obstacle is the need to enhance their skills and abilities in analyzing problems related to these operations. Another factor to consider is the language used in instruction, a crucial aspect of education. Teachers convey information and guidance to students using language during the learning process. There is often an assumption that students are familiar with or can quickly grasp the language used in the classroom, which ultimately contributes to achieving desired educational outcomes.

Teachers must craft interventions to help the learners implement face-to-face classes as part of the new normal. Teachers should think of something to integrate the strategy for struggling learners – considered 21st-century learners. There is a need for collaboration between teachers, stakeholders, and parents to deliver quality education. They will work as partners to uplift the academic performance of struggling learners despite the challenges brought by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Santos (2019) cited that Four Fundamental Operations MTB Task Cards are one way to practice four fundamental operations using task cards to discuss new situations. Having students meaningfully think about problems they could potentially be in helps them to construct innovative ways to improve their skills in four fundamental operations. Four Fundamental Operations MTB Task Cards became significant in maintaining the students' motivation despite their poor grasp of ideas and processes from a highly verbal lecture.

The study of Montales (2020) discovered that using MTB Task Cards can enhance students' math skills, even with limited parental assistance during a pandemic. Additionally, Pillos et al. (2020) observed that incorporating the Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction for teaching the four basic mathematical operations enhances students' understanding and problem-solving abilities in Math. UNESCO advocates for using mother tongue instruction to enhance the quality of education by capitalizing on the knowledge and experience of both learners and educators.

The abovementioned studies used MTB Tasks in their provinces, and their results showed the effectiveness of the MTB Task Cards. The researcher was prompted to use MTB Tasks Cards to determine its effectiveness and whether this strategy is also effective in her school where MTB Tasks was implemented. In addition, the researcher's root cause analysis showed that most Grade 7 students need more understanding of fundamental mathematics, which impacts their ability to grasp the lessons outlined in the Essential Learning Competencies for the first quarter. By mastering the fundamentals of mathematics, students can build a solid foundation and effectively comprehend more advanced mathematical concepts.

Hence, the study provides a generic pedagogical-based strategy to reach out to Grade 7 learners to remediate learning gaps since they were in Grade 5 when the pandemic occurred. Teachers need to help this type of student and hone them to become academically proficient during the post-pandemic. The study aims to remediate the learning gaps of Grade 7 students using MTB-Task Cards.

Research Questions

This study generally aimed to use MTB-Task Cards to remediate learning gaps in Grade 7 mathematics, leading to a proposed handbook for the development, production, and utilization of MTB-Task Cards. Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions.

1. What are the least mastered learning competencies (based on MELCs) Mathematics 7 for the 1st and 2nd quarter of the school year 2023-2024 during the first and second quarter?
2. What is the level of performance in Mathematics of Grade 7 Learners before and after implementing MTB-Task Cards from the identified least learned competencies during the first and second quarters?
3. What is the mean gain performance of grade 7 learners after implementing the MTB Task Card during the first and second quarters?
4. Is there a significant difference between actual accomplishment and target level of mastery after the implementation of MTB-task card?
5. Based on the study's findings, what Handbook on the Rules and Guidelines in the Development, Production and Utilization of MTB-Task Cards that the researcher can be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a quasi-experimental approach to evaluate interventions without randomization. It used a pre-test and post-test design to measure the desired effect before and after exposing a non-random group of participants to a specific intervention. The research aimed to address the learning gaps of Grade 7 students using MTB-Task Cards. Pre-tests and post-tests were administered before and after the implementation of MTB-Task Cards, and any significant differences were analyzed. The expected outcome was the development of MTB-Task Cards and an intervention program, resulting in improved skills for Grade 7 learners.

Respondents

The study used a total enumeration technique to select Grade 7 learners at Emilio V. Quizon National High School, San Andres, Quezon, who were identified as having the most significant number of least mastered Mathematics competencies for the School Year 2022-2023. The study was organized into three sections: A, B, and C, each with 45 students, resulting in a total population of 135 Grade 7 students. This approach minimized selection bias and ensured representativeness of the population. All 45 students from each section were selected to participate, resulting in 135 respondents. This approach ensured that every individual had an equal chance of being selected as a respondent.

Instruments

This research utilized a researcher-made test question and an MTB Task Card as the primary data-gathering instrument for a study on the least learned competency of Grade 7 students based on MELCs. The MTB Task Card was designed to cover the most crucial learning competencies in the first quarter. The test consisted of 30 questions closely aligned with the most crucial learning competencies.

The development of task cards for mathematics instruction incorporates several unique features that contribute to their effectiveness in promoting mathematical learning and mastery of competencies. The "Expectations" section outlines specific learning objectives or competencies students are expected to achieve, aligning with curriculum standards or learning outcomes. The "Explanation" section provides clear and concise explanations of mathematical concepts, strategies, or procedures relevant to the given task. The "Exercises" section presents practice problems or activities for students to complete, reinforcing the mathematical concepts covered in the Explanation section. The "Estimation/Computation Space" is a designated area on the task cards where students can perform calculations, show their work, or provide written responses to the exercises.

Task cards are modular learning resources that can be easily adapted to target specific mathematical concepts or competencies, allowing for differentiated instruction and personalized learning experiences. They are designed to be engaging and interactive, fostering active participation and problem-solving skills among students. Additionally, they align with Formative Assessment and Feedback, providing ongoing feedback on students' progress and understanding.

The validation process for the researcher-made test questions and MTB Task Cards involved multiple stages and experts to ensure comprehensive feedback and refinement. The initial presentation to the evaluator allowed for an initial assessment of the material's content, format, and clarity. After comprehensive validation, suggestions and recommendations were incorporated into the test questions and task cards, allowing for refinement and improvement based on expert input. The final versions of the test questions and task cards were presented to the evaluator for a final review, ensuring all feedback was addressed and the materials were polished and ready for use.

Procedure

The researcher obtained permission from the PSDS of the San Andres District to conduct a study using MTB-Task Cards to address learning gaps among Grade 7 students at Emilio V. Quizon National High School. The study involved three sections, enrolled in the 2023-2024 school year. A pre-test was conducted before the MTB-Task Cards were used, followed by a post-test with 30 questions. The test material was tested for content validity by a master's teacher in mathematics. The post-test was conducted to evaluate the students' performance using the MTB-Task Cards. The researcher conducted a pilot implementation of the MTB-Task Cards in other districts, ensuring content validity. A guide was formulated to implement the strategies before immersion.

Data Analysis

In SOP 1, the least mastered learning competencies (based on MELCs) in Mathematics 7 for the 1st and 2nd quarters of the School Year 2023-2024 were identified. The level of performance of Grade 7 students in Mathematics The data were analyzed using mean percentage scores, frequency counts and using scale for mastery level.

Table 1. *Scale for Mastery Level in Mathematics 7*

<i>Range</i>	<i>Adjectival Equivalent</i>
96%-100%	Mastered
86%-95%	Closely Approximating Mastery
66%-85%	Moving Towards Mastery
35%-65%	Average Near Mastery
15%-34%	Low Mastery
5%-14%	Very low Mastery
0%-4%	Absolutely No Mastery

While SOP 2, before and after implementing MTB-Math Cards to address these least learned competencies, was assessed during the first and second quarters treated using t-test. On the other hand, in SOP 3 the mean gain in performance of Grade 7 learners after implementing the MTB Task Card. The data were analyzed using mean percentage scores, frequency counts, and a performance scale for learners.

Table 2. *Scale for Learners' Performance in Mathematics 7*

Range	Adjectival Equivalent
90%-100%	Outstanding
85%-89%	Very Satisfactory
80%-84%	Satisfactory
75%-79%	Fairly Satisfactory
74 % below	Did Not Meet Expectations

While in SOP 4, the significant difference between the actual accomplishments of students and the target level of mastery after implementing the MTB-Task Card was tested using Levene's Test. This test helped determine the effectiveness of the MTB-Task Card intervention in improving student mastery of the least learned competencies in Mathematics.

Results and Discussion

Part I. Least Mastered Learning Competencies of Learners in Mathematics 7

First Quarter and Second Quarter of the School Year 2023-2024 Based On MELCS

Table 3. *Least Mastered Learning Competencies on Mathematics 7 Learners for the 1st and 2nd Quarter of the School Year 2023-2024 based on the MPS Result of Learners' Performance*

Quarter	Content Standard	Most Essential Learning Competencies	MPS (%)	Descriptive Interpretation
1st quarter	Demonstrates understanding of key concepts of sets and the real number system	1. performs fundamental operations on integers	32.00	Low Mastery
		2. illustrates different properties of operation on the set of integers	32.00	Low Mastery
		3. estimates the square roots	34.00	Low Mastery
		4. solves problems involving sets with the use of the Venn Diagram and	31.00	Low Mastery
		5. Solves problems involving real numbers.	30.00	Low Mastery
2nd quarter	Demonstrates understanding of key concepts of algebraic expressions, the properties of real numbers as applied in linear equations and inequalities in one variable.	1. Evaluates algebraic expressions for given values of the variables	34.00	Low Mastery
		2. adds and subtracts polynomials	34.00	Low Mastery
		3. derives the laws of exponent	33.00	Low Mastery
		4. multiplies and divides polynomials	29.00	Low Mastery
		5. Solves problems involving equations and inequalities in one variable.	29.00	Low Mastery
Overall Mean Percentage Score			31.80	Low Mastery

Legend: 96-100 Mastered; 86-95 Closely Approximating Mastery; 66-85 Moving Towards Mastery; 35-65 Average Near Mastery; 15-34 Low Mastery; 5-14 Very Low Mastery; 0-4 Absolutely No Mastery

Table 3 presents the least mastered learning competencies in Mathematics 7 learners for the 1st and 2nd quarters of the school year 2023-2024, based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). The competencies are identified as the least learned after teaching it to the students based on the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) obtained by the learners after each quarter. These competencies are categorized into two main content areas: understanding critical concepts of sets and the actual number system and understanding key concepts of algebraic expressions, properties of real numbers, linear equations, and inequalities in one variable.

In the first quarter, learners struggled the most with competencies related to "performing fundamental operations on integers," "illustrating different properties of operations on the set of integers," "estimating square roots, solving problems involving sets using Venn Diagrams," and "solving problems involving real numbers." All these competencies were classified as having low mastery levels, with Mean Percentage Scores (MPS) ranging from 30% to 34%.

In the second quarter, the least mastered competencies included "evaluating algebraic expressions for given values of variables," "adding and subtracting polynomials, deriving laws of exponents," "multiplying and dividing polynomials," and "solving problems involving equations and inequalities in one variable." Like the first content area, these competencies also exhibited low mastery levels, with MPS ranging from 29% to 34%. The overall Mean Percentage Score for the least mastered competencies across both content areas was 31.80%, indicating a low mastery level among the learners.

Based on the above least mastered competencies, the COVID-19 pandemic has led to a significant decrease in the mastery of mathematical competencies among Grade 7 learners. This is attributed to disruptions in learning continuity, limited interaction and engagement, lack of hands-on activities, restricted access to support services, technological barriers, and emotional and psychological impacts. Traditional classroom learning has been replaced with modular distance learning, which may have disrupted students' learning experiences, especially in mathematics. The pandemic has also exacerbated learning gaps, particularly for disadvantaged or remote students. Additionally, the pandemic has had a significant emotional and psychological impact on students, affecting their ability to

focus and engage in learning activities. Targeted interventions are highly needed to address these challenges.

Hence, to address the least mastered competencies, diagnostic tests can be utilized to identify specific areas of weakness and tailor interventions accordingly. Diagnostic tests can help teachers pinpoint individual and collective areas of difficulty, allowing for targeted instruction and remediation. By implementing diagnostic tests to identify the root causes of learners' struggles, educators can implement effective teaching strategies, provide additional practice opportunities, offer personalized support, and adjust instructional materials to meet the learners' needs better. Additionally, ongoing assessment and feedback mechanisms can help track progress and ensure that interventions effectively improve student mastery of the identified competencies. In support, Herrera and Dio (2016) identified that students need a greater understanding of solving math word problems, indicating low proficiency. In response, mathematics teachers focus on addressing the areas where students struggle to reach a competency level of 75%. To achieve this, the implementation of a tailored intervention plan is essential. Students' mathematical skills can be effectively enhanced by integrating diverse exercises into remedial tutoring sessions (Jubilo, 2020).

In conclusion, the findings from Table 3 indicate that learners have least mastered several learning competencies in Mathematics 7 during the 1st and 2nd Quarter of the School Year 2023-2024. The low overall percentage score suggests that learners may struggle to comprehend and effectively utilize these competencies in different mathematical topics. Additional effort, support, and targeted interventions are necessary to address these challenges. Teachers should offer consistent interventions through small-group instruction and engaging strategies to help learners overcome difficulties and achieve higher competency levels.

Furthermore, Mathematics teachers need to pay special attention to students' unmastered abilities and create customized intervention plans, such as remedial tutoring with various exercises, to improve their skills in mathematics. By implementing these strategies, learners can be guided towards mastery in the least mastered learning competencies in Mathematics 7.

PART II. Level of Performance in Mathematics of Grade 7 Learners Before and After the Implementation of MTB-Task Cards

Table 4. *Level of Performance in Mathematics of Grade 7 Learners Before and After the Implementation of MTB-Task Cards*

Quarter	Least Mastered Learning Competencies	Pre-test		Post-test		Difference (Posttest-Pretest)
		Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	
1st Quarter	1. performs fundamental operations on integers	31.00	DNME	83.70	Satisfactory	52.70
	2. illustrates different properties of operation on the set of integers	30.00	DNME	82.80	Satisfactory	52.80
	3. estimates the square roots	31.00	DNME	84.70	Satisfactory	53.70
	4. solves problems involving sets with the use of the Venn Diagram and	30.00	DNME	83.40	Satisfactory	53.40
	5. Solves problems involving real numbers.	30.00	DNME	83.70	Satisfactory	53.70
Composite Mean/Mean Difference		30.40		83.66		53.26
2nd quarter	1. evaluates algebraic expressions for given values of the variables	30.00	DNME	82.90	Satisfactory	52.90
	2. adds and subtracts polynomials	31.00	DNME	82.70	Satisfactory	51.70
	3. derives the laws of exponent	32.00	DNME	83.90	Satisfactory	51.90
	4. multiplies and divides polynomials and	30.00	DNME	83.10	Satisfactory	53.10
	5. Solves problems involving equations and inequalities in one variable.	31.00	DNME	83.30	Satisfactory	52.10
Composite Mean/Mean Difference		30.8	DNME	83.18	Satisfactory	52.38
Grand Mean		30.6	DNME	83.42	Satisfactory	52.82

Legend: 90%-100% Outstanding (O); 85%-89% Very Satisfactory (VS); 80%-84% Satisfactory (S); 75%-79% Fairly Satisfactory (FS); 74% Below Did Not Meet Expectations (DNME)

The table presents the level of performance in mathematics of Grade 7 students before and after the implementation of MTB-Task Cards, focusing on specific learning competencies. The competencies are categorized based on whether the students least mastered them. The pre-test and post-test scores are provided along with the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) and the Degree of Improvement (DI) to measure between the difference in performance from the pre-test to the post-test.

The table indicates an improvement in the performance of Grade 7 students in various mathematical competencies after implementing MTB-Task Cards. The difference between the performance are measured in terms of percentage increase from pre-test to post-test. Generally, most competencies show significant improvements, moving from a "Did Not Meet Expectations" level to a "Satisfactory" level after the intervention. This suggests that the MTB-Task Cards have positively impacted students' understanding and mastery of the specified mathematical concepts and skills.

Furthermore, MTB Task Cards have significantly improved competency mastery in mathematical subjects. MTB Task Cards offer a structured approach to practicing mathematical concepts, focusing on specific skills or competencies that initially struggled. They often incorporate visual representations, diagrams, and illustrations to enhance understanding and facilitate problem-solving. MTB Task Cards feature progressive difficulty levels, allowing learners to gradually progress from foundational to more advanced concepts. They are designed to be interactive and engaging, encouraging active participation and problem-solving skills. They can be customized to meet the diverse needs of learners, providing differentiated instruction and support. They also include built-in mechanisms for immediate feedback, promoting metacognition and self-regulated learning. MTB Task Cards are often integrated into instructional practices, providing consistent support for learners to practice and master essential competencies over time.

In support of the results, Mese and Sevilen (2021) researched using the mother tongue in teaching mathematics. They found that learners' motivation levels are lower when they skip classes or do not participate in activities due to the language and subject matter unmotivating them. This leads to poor quality education, which can unequally impact vulnerable groups. Additionally, language enables students to play an active role in various communities of learners within and beyond the classroom.

In conclusion, using MTB-Task Cards was crucial in improving students' engagement and motivation in Mathematics. Students could actively participate and understand the subject matter better by utilizing their mother tongue in the form of task cards. This resulted in a significant improvement in their academic performance, as seen in the post-test scores.

Part III. Mean Gain Performance of Grade 7 Learners After the Implementation of MTB-Task Card

Table 5 shows that implementing the MTB Task Card effectively improved the mastery levels of Grade 7 learners. More specifically, practical gains were noted in the essential learning competencies visited in the study's 1st and 2nd quarters.

Table 5. Gain Performance of Grade 7 Learners After the Implementation of MTB Task Card

<i>Quarter</i>	<i>Least Mastered Essential Learning Competencies</i>	<i>Actual Accomplishment (MPS)</i>	<i>Target Level of Mastery (%)</i>	<i>Gain (Actual Accomplishment - Target Level of Mastery)</i>
1st quarter	1. Performs Fundamental Operations on Integers	83.70	80	3.70
	2. Illustrates Different Properties of Operation on The Set of Integers	82.80		2.80
	3. Estimates the square root of a whole number to the nearest hundredth.	84.70		4.70
	4. Represents Real-Life Situations and Solves Problems Involving Real Numbers	83.40		3.40
	5. Solves Problems Involving Sets with The Use of Venn Diagram	83.70		3.70
	Composite Mean/Mean Gain	83.66		3.66
2nd quarter	1. Evaluates algebraic expressions for given values of the Variables	82.90	80	2.90
	2. Adds and subtracts polynomials	82.70		2.70
	3. Derives the laws of exponent	83.90		3.90
	4. Multiplies and divides polynomials	83.10		3.10
	5. Solves problems involving equations and inequalities in one variable	83.30		3.30
	Composite Mean/Mean Gain	83.18		3.18
	Grand Mean	83.42		3.42

In the 1st quarter, the data highlights the performance of Grade 7 Learners who have at least mastered essential learning competencies, mainly focusing on their mastery of fundamental mathematical concepts before and after intervention. Across the five competencies assessed, Learners demonstrated mastery levels ranging from 82.8% to 84.7%, which exceeded the 80% target accomplishment. This indicates a solid foundational understanding of these mathematical concepts among the Learners. Specifically, in performing fundamental operations on integers, illustrating properties of operations on the set of integers, estimating square roots, representing real-life situations, and solving problems involving sets with the use of Venn diagrams, Learners surpassed the target mastery level by margins ranging from 2.8% to 4.7%. These gains suggest that the Learners have not only met but exceeded the expected level of proficiency in these areas. Such outcomes indicate effective teaching strategies and the Learners' successful assimilation of mathematical concepts. Moving forward, educators may focus on maintaining and further building upon this strong foundation to ensure continued academic growth and success in mathematics.

In the 2nd quarter, the data provides insights into the performance of Grade 7 Learners who have at least mastered essential learning competencies, explicitly focusing on their proficiency in various mathematical concepts before and after intervention. Across the five competencies assessed, Learners demonstrated mastery levels ranging from 82.7% to 83.9%. Notably, all competencies exceeded the 80% target accomplishment, indicating a solid understanding of these mathematical concepts among the Learners. Specifically, in evaluating algebraic expressions, adding and subtracting polynomials, deriving the laws of exponents, multiplying and dividing polynomials, and solving problems involving equations and inequalities in one variable, Learners surpassed the target mastery level by margins ranging from 2.7% to 3.9%. These gains suggest significant improvement and achievement beyond the expected level of proficiency in these areas. The outcomes reflect effective teaching strategies and the Learners' successful assimilation of mathematical concepts, contributing to their overall academic growth and success in mathematics. Reinforcing and building upon these foundational skills will be essential to sustain and enhance student learning in subsequent quarters.

These findings underscore the role of targeted interventions, such as using the MTB Task Card, in enhancing Learners' performance and understanding of mathematics concepts. Indeed, through such structured instructional activities and related exercises, educators can support the mastery and retention of mathematics content among Learners.

Furthermore, Grade 7 learners showed significant performance gains after using MTB Task Cards. These were due to targeted practice, visual representation, interactive learning experience, differentiated instruction, and immediate feedback. The task cards reinforced essential mathematical concepts, such as fundamental operations on integers and problem-solving techniques. They also provided visual representations and real-life contexts, enhancing conceptual understanding. The interactive format encouraged active participation, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. MTB Task Cards can be customized to meet diverse learners' needs, providing differentiated instruction and support. The immediate feedback enabled learners to self-assess their understanding and identify areas for improvement. These outcomes demonstrate the effectiveness of MTB Task Cards as a valuable instructional tool for promoting academic growth and success in mathematics.

The results of Montale's (2020) study further substantiate the findings provided in Table 5, which confirm that implementing MTB-Task Cards has dramatically affected the development of Learners' problem-solving skills within the divisibility criterion. Therefore, the Task Card was effective in tackling such problems. This claim is consistent with the evidence of enhanced mastery levels in Table 5, presented across the multiple mathematical criteria. Thus, such targeted instructional activities as task cards correspond to efficient mathematical interventions, significantly influencing Learners' performance and skill in specific domains.

Englis and Boholano (2022) also conducted a study and discovered that utilizing the mother tongue in Mathematics instruction is a successful strategy for gaining mathematical knowledge. The teachers were adequately trained and employed suitable teaching materials. Moreover, the contextualized and innovative approach to teaching Mathematics using the mother tongue aided in developing fundamental mathematical skills. This conclusion was supported by the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores.

In conclusion, the data analysis demonstrates a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores after implementing MTB Tasks Cards. This signifies that the instructional tool has positively influenced the academic performance of Grade 7 Learners, provided targeted practice, and fostered a more interactive learning experience.

Part IV. Significant Difference Between the Actual Accomplishment and Target Level of Mastery After Implementation of the MTB-Task Card

Table 6. A Statistical Table showing the Significant Difference Between Actual Accomplishment and Target Mastery

		<i>Independent Samples Test</i>						
		<i>Levene's Test for Equality of Variances</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>	
score	Equal variances assumed	16.660	.001	17.817	18	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Equal variances are not assumed.			17.817	9.000	.000		

Table 6 presents the results of an Independent Samples Test conducted to examine the significant difference between actual accomplishment and the target level of mastery. Levene's Test for Equality of Variances was used to assess whether the assumption of

equal variances across groups was met.

The table indicates that the Levene's Test resulted in a significant p-value of 0.000, indicating that the assumption of equal variances was violated. Therefore, the "Equal variances not assumed" row is considered for interpretation.

The significance level (p-value) for comparing actual accomplishment and target mastery is 0.000. Since this p-value is less than the significance level (typically set at 0.05), it suggests a statistically significant difference between actual accomplishment and the target level of mastery.

The statistically significant difference between actual accomplishment and target mastery implies that the instructional interventions or educational programs implemented had a measurable impact on student achievement. It suggests that Learners could surpass or fall short of the target level of mastery in a statistically meaningful way, highlighting the effectiveness of the interventions in either meeting or deviating from the intended learning outcomes.

The findings supported by Montales (2020) revealed a significant difference between actual accomplishment and target mastery, suggesting discrepancies between Learners' current levels of achievement and educational standards. This discrepancy is crucial for instructional decisions, curriculum development, and intervention strategies. If Learners consistently exceed target mastery levels, educators may adjust instructional strategies, while if they fall short, targeted interventions may be implemented. The study underscores the importance of ongoing assessment, data-driven decision-making, and continuous improvement efforts in education to ensure all Learners achieve their full potential and meet learning goals.

In conclusion, the findings indicate that the MTB-Task Card intervention strategy significantly contributed to improving learners' academic performance. Since the null hypothesis was rejected, it means that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that there was a meaningful improvement in academic performance compared to the target mastery level. Therefore, the MTB-Task Card intervention effectively improves learners' academic achievement.

PART V. MTB-Task Cards Handbook

The MTB-Task Cards Handbook is an indispensable resource for educators seeking to enhance student learning outcomes by effectively utilizing MTB-Task Cards. As educators navigate the complexities of modern educational practices, MTB-Task Cards offer a versatile and innovative approach to delivering targeted instruction and fostering active learning experiences. Aligning with specific learning objectives and essential competencies outlined in curriculum standards, MTB-Task Cards Handbook provide educators with a structured framework for addressing diverse learning needs and promoting conceptual understanding among Learners.

The introduction sets the stage for the comprehensive exploration of MTB-Task Cards, highlighting their significance in today's educational landscape and their transformative potential for enhancing classroom instruction. Emphasizing the interactive nature of MTB-Task Cards, the handbook underscores their role in promoting critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and conceptual understanding among Learners.

In the development section, the handbook outlines critical considerations for creating effective MTB-Task Cards, including alignment with learning objectives, clear content development, and visually appealing graphic design and layout. By adhering to these guidelines, educators can ensure the relevance, clarity, and engagement of MTB-Task Cards, thereby maximizing their effectiveness as instructional tools.

The production section underscores the importance of quality assurance, printing, packaging, and accessibility in the production process. Prioritizing durability, accessibility, and clarity in production, educators can guarantee the longevity and effectiveness of MTB-Task Cards in classroom settings.

Finally, the utilization section offers practical strategies for integrating MTB-Task Cards into lesson plans, differentiating instruction to meet diverse learning needs, and leveraging MTB-Task Cards for assessment and feedback. Educators can optimize student engagement, comprehension, and academic success by incorporating MTB-Task Cards into instructional practices.

In conclusion, the MTB-Task Cards Handbook equips educators with the knowledge and resources needed to harness the full potential of MTB-Task Cards in educational settings. Through collaborative effort and adherence to the guidelines outlined in this handbook, educators can empower Learners to succeed academically and thrive in today's ever-evolving learning environments.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions can be drawn regarding the effect of using MTB Task Cards in teaching Grade 7 competencies.

The study identified the least mastered learning competencies in Mathematics among Grade 7 learners for both the 1st and 2nd quarters of the school year 2023-2024 based on MELCS. Notable improvements were observed across various mathematical tasks, highlighting the effectiveness of the instructional methods.

Significant improvements were revealed in the level of performance in Mathematics among Grade 7 learners following the

implementation of MTB-Task Cards during both quarters. Learners demonstrated enhanced proficiency in various competencies, with gains exceeding expectations and indicating a solid understanding of the material.

The data revealed a positive gain in the performance of Grade 7 learners after implementing MTB Task Cards during both quarters. Mastery levels exceeded target accomplishment, reflecting effective teaching strategies and underscoring the impact of MTB-Task Cards on Learners' academic performance.

There was a significant difference between actual accomplishment and the target level of mastery after the implementation of MTB-Task Cards, as indicated by a p-value of 0.000. This suggests that the intervention significantly enhanced learner's academic performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Establishing rules and guidelines in developing, producing, and utilizing MTB-Task Cards is crucial for ensuring consistency, accuracy, and effectiveness in their implementation. These guidelines support standardized approaches, curriculum alignment, quality production, and effective utilization in the classroom, ultimately enhancing learning experiences and outcomes for both educators and Learners.

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